

Integrating variable retention systems into strategic forest management to deal with conservation biodiversity objectives

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ABSTRACT

For the past few decades, the integration of biodiversity conservation into forest management has constituted an important challenge, since the new forest management models should make conservation objectives compatible with production issues. In many countries, timber production is no longer the main ecosystem service provided, thus other aspects such as biodiversity conservation are taken into account. One of the strategies developed to do so is to define, at the stand level, areas where final cuttings are not allowed. These areas can be found dispersed or aggregated (comprised of multiple stands) throughout the forest, helping to maintain a percentage of mature forest that fulfils conservation goals. In this study, we have developed a strategic forest planning model that allows us to integrate several retention systems compared to the business-as-usual treatment traditionally used. Production, technical and environmental criteria have been considered in order to analyse the degree of conflict between them by designing a pay-off matrix. Using multicriteria techniques conflicting objectives were assessed, and decision makers' interactions have been introduced. These interactions range from criteria selection to the allocation of preferential weights to each criterion until the best solution among a set of possible alternatives is identified. The presented analytical procedure is based on the extended goal programming method applied in an exemplary forest in central Spain. Our results show that the proposed methodology allows deriving solutions that are acceptable for decision makers while estimating physical and economic opportunity costs of conservation measures in timber volume and Euros respectively.

1. Introduction

In the last few decades, and in different parts of the world, a series of silvicultural tools and alternatives have been proposed to integrate additional objectives alongside timber production into forest management, contributing to the idea of multifunctionality associated with forest systems (Gustafsson et al., 2010; Puettmann et al., 2015). In many cases, such multifunctionality is achieved by modifying harvesting systems, reducing the areas affected by final cuttings corresponding to the final felling in a series of cuts (Matthews, 1989), and leaving parts of the Forest perpetually uncut. These approaches were suggested in Europe many years ago (Hundeshagen, 1826), but recently in some parts of the world, the potential benefits of these new “multi-aged” or “many-aged forests” have been defined (O'Hara, 2014; Puettmann et al., 2015). Although for some authors these new silvicultural practices (like retention systems) can be made compatible with the idea of a normal forest (Deal et al., 2013), in these cases the classic management objectives are no longer pursued. In any case, these

retention systems usually lead to a decrease in the number and intensity of the cuttings and, thus, a reduction in the monetary profits associated with these forest systems.

Biodiversity conservation is one of the objectives that are increasingly required alongside timber production. To achieve biodiversity conservation, forest management is being oriented towards multifunctional approaches. The solutions proposed include introducing certain constraints on the initial management plan, or using multicriteria methods that permit the simultaneous optimization of both outputs (Bertomeu and Romero, 2001). Consequently, for over 25 years, some authors have been recommending management systems in which specific areas are left uncut or retained in order to give shelter to certain species of fauna. This idea, known first as *Green-Tree Retention* (GTR), has spread out from the west coast of the U.S.A. to other countries (Gustafsson et al., 2012), and there is now abundant literature on it (Gustafsson et al., 2010; Rosenvald and Löhmus, 2008; Baker et al., 2013; Fedrowitz et al., 2014). However, in the last few years, this idea has been popularized as *Variable Retention* (VR), through the

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creation of multi-aged stands (O'Hara, 2014), increasing old-growth structures in order to favour other ecosystem services (Bauhus et al., 2009), and improving the complexity of managed forests. Shea et al. (2017) recently showed how this silvicultural strategy is effective for conserving the biodiversity at a landscape scale, especially with regard to moderate fragmentation levels (Mori et al., 2017), while Augustynczyk et al. (2018) demonstrated the same approach at the stand level. Finally, it has been seen that combining the retained areas with a more intensive management can offer results that compete economically with traditional management forms (Bravo and Diaz-Balteiro, 2004).

This silvicultural alternative that mitigates the effects of the final cuttings in biodiversity could be perfectly valid when we are faced with cases where the conservation of certain wildlife species is a key objective in forest management. Its suitable flexibility justifies its use in different forest systems, particularly in boreal and temperate areas (Gustafsson et al., 2012). In addition, some authors agree that it is an essential tool to achieve an ecologically sustainable forest management (Lindenmayer et al., 2012) in a multifunctional context.

At this point, it would be interesting to ask whether variable retention criteria have been successfully integrated as an objective into strategic planning models that attempt to handle problems such as the development of optimal harvest schedules. As far as we know, advances in this direction have been somewhat scant. Wikström and Eriksson (2000) used different heuristics, and in one of the two sub problems analysed, targets associated with GTR were introduced. Pukkala (2006) applied a model based on the Hooke and Jeeves (1961) algorithm to simulate a GTR management in a Norway spruce plantation. In some studies, classic optimization models were proposed in which some of the possible alternatives referred to retention scenarios (Bergseng et al., 2012; Søvde et al., 2014). Wagner et al. (2010) proposed two spatial optimization models in GTR problems and pointed out the need to use multicriteria techniques for this type of problem. Finally, Bouchard and Garet (2014) developed a strategic approach based on Model II (Johnson and Scheurman, 1977), where timber production is optimized but the retention objective is introduced as a constraint.

Besides, it should be emphasized that the idea of using optimization tools for integrating conservation objectives into forest management has been applied for some decades. However, most studies use mono-objective approaches to handling these problems, although more and more hybrid models (combining two or more techniques) are being used to address this objective (Ezquerro et al., 2016). Some of these studies employed different multicriteria techniques but did not integrate any explicit retention objectives into the analyses (Schwenk et al., 2012; Bagdon et al., 2016).

The case study where this model was applied is a forest system whose management was (since the end of the 19th century) inspired by the idea of a normal forest. However, conservation objectives in the region are rapidly gaining importance due to the presence of protected species, such as the population of black vultures. A series of measures have been incorporated to preserve those populations and facilitate their future development, mainly focusing on minimizing the disturbances caused by the forest operations carried out in the area. Accordingly, even without defining it as such in the forest management plans, retention in volume is already applied in the region. Through the preferred silvicultural practice (shelterwood system, no clearcutting), commercial cuttings are banned around the existing black vulture nests and, more recently, in areas newly declared as a National Park.

The main objective of this study is to show an approach for addressing conservation objectives in no cutting areas through variable retention systems. We measured the total retained area (both dispersed and aggregated area) and the amount retained in each period, ensuring a non-declining retained area over the planning horizon. The newly developed criteria will be integrated into a strategic forest planning model. The impact of these criteria on other objectives usually considered in productive forest management (volume, net present value),

technical (normal forest criteria), or environmental issues (carbon sequestration) will be evaluated. For this purpose, first, the trade-off between all the criteria considered will be assessed. Then, in order to apply an extended goal programming model, a target linked to each criterion will be defined, integrating the preferences of a decision-maker. The proposed models will be able to provide “satisficing” solutions that are directly influenced by the decision makers' preferences.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Case study

Valsaín forest covers a surface of 7,622 ha and is located in the Central Mountain Range of Spain. It is an emblematic forest in Spanish forestry history, which belongs to the State, being Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) its main tree species. The first forest management plan dates from 1889, and since then its primary objective has been timber production and keeping up the initial idea of obtaining a normal forest structure, although a fully regulated forest has not yet been achieved. Its strategic planning was not done by using optimizing tools, but by applying classic European management methods. Its traditional silvicultural treatment is based on a uniform shelterwood system with a rotation of 120 years and, since the 1980's, an extended regeneration period of 40 years. The forest is formed by 288 stands which constitute the management units in accordance with the current forest management plan (2010–2020). In recent years, the management has become more multifunctional and nowadays it pays close attention to aspects like biodiversity conservation (Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2017). In fact, since 2013, part of the forest (3,326 ha) has been included in a new National Park, where commercial cuttings have been forbidden.

Regarding the spatial organisation of areas in which cuttings have been banned (retention areas) we have considered the inclusion of three retention options at stand level. This scale has been proposed based on the management units used in this study. In the first option, these areas can be retained as dispersed trees throughout the stand (computing as a 5% of the stand's area after final cuttings). In the second option, residual trees are concentrated in patches (retaining a percentage or the entire area of the stand as aggregated retention). The third option combines the two previous options (dispersed and aggregated retention). This last option has been proposed as the best strategy according to Lindenmayer and Franklin (2002, pp. 177). Thus, we have considered the benefits of combining retention strategies over a long-term horizon, including dispersed and aggregated trees in the case study. Besides, each retention type offers different potential benefits for biodiversity conservation. Although many studies have pointed out the benefits of variable retention (i.e., Franklin et al., 1997; Lindenmayer and Franklin, 2002; Rosenvald and Löhmus, 2008), only a few singularized the advantages of each retention type. Thus, while Gustafsson et al. (2012) suggested a combination of intact patches and dispersed trees in order to select structural attributes from the forest, Ribe (2005) indicated that important dispersed retention areas provide greater scenic beauty than aggregated retention. Finally, in other studies (Venier et al., 2015), aggregated retention appears to be efficient in a single case study providing mature forest habitats for some breeding forest birds.

In the forest studied (Valsaín forest), there is a breeding colony of black vultures, (*Aegypius monachus* (Linnaeus, 1766)), an umbrella species (Iglesias-Merchán et al., 2016), which is catalogued as “near threatened” at world level (Moreno-Opo et al., 2012). This species needs large areas of an appropriate habitat for its well-being (Morán-López et al., 2006), so that a critical aspect in forest management in recent years has been the reduction in the effective cutting area. In this way, when a nest is found, a restricted area without management of 3.14 ha around each nest is established. As shown in Fig. 1, the number of bird pairs has tended to increase, and it has been assumed that, until now, this has not substantially affected timber production.

Fig. 1. Black vulture species evolution (2000–2017) in Valsaín forest. Source: Autonomous Agency of National Parks (OAPN).

However, it should be noted that the number of nests used over time by the same pair is variable. In this way, black vultures need to dispose of other trees near their nests that are suitable for building new ones since they frequently change nests from year to year (De la Puente, 2007). In fact, around each black vulture nest, a buffer protection of a 100 m radius is left and not usually cut, and forestry operations are forbidden in a 500 meter radius circle during the most sensitive periods that are vital for the survival of these species. Therefore, the area initially retained in the forest reaches up to 411 ha and, although at the moment there are no specific studies quantifying the positive impact of these retained areas on the population of this species. However, it is assumed that its abundance will increase with the silvicultural systems linked to variable retention (Shea et al., 2017).

2.2. Methodology

In order to clarify the different steps followed, the methodology used is summarized in a flow chart in Fig. 2, which is valid for any problem of a similar nature. The different phases of that flowchart are also detailed.

Fig. 2. Flow chart methodology process.

2.2.1. Choosing criteria

Since the methodology has to be adapted to various aspects to be considered in Valsaín forest, it needs to include different criteria that have been grouped into three large blocks or pillars (environmental, technical and productive), as shown in Fig. 2. First, the environmental block includes those criteria associated with the area retained over the planning horizon (RA) and how this area is structured over time. What is intended is that the retained area should be non-declining (NDRA) in order to ensure an increasing retained area in each period into which the planning horizon is divided, with respect to the previous period. Carbon balance (C), one of the main ecosystem services demanded in this forest (Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2017), is also included in this environmental pillar. The carbon used in the optimization models is obtained from the annual balance of the growing stock and the emissions produced after the final cuttings, and it was computed in physical units. Regarding the technical block, those three variables habitually associated with the idea of a normal forest have been considered (Pereira et al., 2015): the equality of volume flows in each period (H); a desirable final inventory structure (F) that guarantees an inventory (in volume terms) that is at least equal to the existing volume at the beginning of the planning horizon; and the area control or regulation for each age class (A). Finally, with respect to the productive pillar, the Net Present Value (NPV) and the volume (VOL) associated with the final cuttings over the planning horizon have been considered. NPV values are obtained considering a real discount rate of 2%. The incomes provided referred only to timber sales, and we have considered different maintenance costs (11.6 €/ha). Following data provided from the current forest management plan, the timber price considered (net of harvesting costs) was 28 €/m³.

2.2.2. Strategic forest planning

Following the flow chart shown in Fig. 2, a strategic forest planning model was designed with a planning horizon of 100 years, divided into 10-year periods, which is a typical timeframe in models with slow-growing species, especially with Scots pine. Sometimes it would be preferable a planning horizon over at least the whole rotation length (i.e., Garcia-Gonzalo et al. 2013), but at least in Europe, many researchers used a 100-years planning horizon to deal with forest management cases (Pukkala and Kurttila 2005; Lundström et al., 2011; Briceño-Elizondo et al., 2008; Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2017). The next step was to establish a strategic harvest scheduling model in relation to Model I methodology (Johnson and Scheurman, 1977), and the information available in the last forest management plan. The rotation length considered was established as a time span ranging between 120 and 180 years, where the lowest limit coincides with the current rotation length in Scots pine in the Sierra de Guadarrama, used by Pardos et al. (2016). However, the upper limit was established at 180 years in an attempt to incorporate prescriptions with a greater rotation length than that usually employed (120 years), in order to provide mature forest habitats, which are essential for the survival of several endangered species (Lindenmayer and Franklin, 2002; Filyushkina et al., 2018). Thus, taking into account the 288 stands, the interval defined for the rotation length, and the way of determining prescriptions in Model I, 3568 prescriptions have been generated.

With regard to the constraints defined in our model, we have included a set of endogenous constraints to ensure that the area chosen by the model cannot exceed the available area in each stand. In addition, two exogenous constraints have been introduced. First, a minimum harvest area of 5 ha in each stand has been proposed to ensure that shelterwood systems (formed by four partial cuttings) are not applied over the planning horizon in small areas. Second, following the indications of the forest manager, it was proposed that the total retained area could not exceed 50% of the case study area.

Table 1
Pay-off Matrix of criteria considered.

Variable	VOL	NPV	H	F	A	RA	NDRA
VOL	4,345	3,638	3,675	2,749	2,956	<u>1,890</u>	2,673
NPV	14,468	37,084	31,660	18,094	16,794	<u>6,240</u>	19,781
H	<u>4,063</u>	1,799	0	663	1,806	1,825	1,195
F	1,189	704	826	120	468	<u>1,612</u>	1,324
A	<u>6,184</u>	4,538	3,510	916	0	3,607	3,138
RA	750	750	840	<u>618</u>	1,363	3,603	2,486
NDRA	40	119	71	71	537	<u>1,825</u>	0
Carbon	3,505	3,768	3,785	4,171	4,087	4,571	4,196
agrR	42	42	170	39	724	3,128	1,874
disR	297	297	258	168	228	64	201

VOL: Harvest volume (10³m³), **NPV:** Net Present Value (10³€), **H:** Even flow harvest volume deviation (10³m³), **F:** Forest ending inventory deviation (10³m³), **A:** Area control deviation (ha), **RA:** Total retained area (considering aggregated, dispersed and black vulture nest protection areas) (ha), **NDRA:** Non-declining retained area deviation (ha), **Carbon:** Carbon balance (10³tC), **agrR:** Aggregated area (ha), **disR:** Dispersed area (ha). Ideal values are shown in bold font, while worst values are shown underlined.

2.2.3. Pay-off matrix

Once the prescriptions have been generated, each criterion is optimized separately, subject to the constraints cited above, and the pay-off matrix is obtained. This is a usual step in the application of multicriteria techniques in forest management problems (Hernandez et al., 2014; Xavier et al., 2015). Table 1 shows the results of this pay-off matrix, where the ideal values (the main diagonal of this matrix) are shown in bold type for each criterion and, the anti-ideal or less desired ones are underlined. Note that for some criteria, deviations are being taken with respect to the ideal value, so that if the ideal value is reached, the value that appears in bold type is 0.

When looking at this matrix, we observed that there is a high degree of conflict between the production and the technical criteria and those associated with variable retention. This conflict would fully justify the employment of a multi-criteria methodology to obtain a solution to the problem since any solution given by the optimization of a single criterion is not acceptable to the decision makers. Apart from that, the retained area criteria and carbon balance show similar solutions when maximizing these objectives. Given that the carbon captured is the criterion that varies the least in percentage when the remaining criteria are optimized, it was decided not to incorporate it into the multicriteria models proposed below, although its value was introduced when optimizing the rest of the criteria in Table 1.

2.2.4. Extended goal programming model

With the aim of obtaining a solution that effectively integrated the different criteria addressed in this problem, we considered appropriate to use an Extended Goal Programming (EGP) model (Romero, 2001, 2004). Among other advantages, this model permitted presenting to the forest manager a range of solutions that went from the most efficient to the most balanced (Uhde et al., 2017), passing through intermediate solutions (Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2013). This method has been successfully used in different forest management problems (Eyvindson, 2012; Giménez et al., 2013; Broz et al., 2016; Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2016). The EGP technical model is presented below, while the model applied to the case study can be seen in Appendix A.

Achievement function

$$Min(1 - \lambda) \cdot D + \lambda \sum_{q=1}^Q w_q \left(\frac{n_q + p_q}{R_q} \right) \tag{1}$$

Goals and constraints

$$f_q(x) + n_q - p_q = t_q^*, q \in \{1, \dots, Q\} \tag{2}$$

$$w_q \cdot \left(\frac{n_q + p_q}{R_q} \right) \leq D \tag{3}$$

$$n_q \geq 0, p_q \geq 0$$

Eq. (1) shows the distinctive element of the EGP models: the so-called achievement function, where λ is a control parameter which takes values inside the closed interval [0, 1], D represents the maximum deviation, while w_q are the preferential weights that the decision maker (DM) assigned to each of the q criteria. The negative and positive deviation variables for each criterion are denoted by n_q and p_q , respectively, and R_q is a normalizing vector attached to each criterion. Eq. (2) states the contribution of each criterion to the achievement of the corresponding target, while Eq. (3) links each normalized and weighted goal with the maximum deviation. By modifying the values assigned to the parameter λ , Model (1)–(3) provides different solutions. Here we have considered three of them. For $\lambda = 0$, the model provides the solution corresponding to the “most balanced achievement”, while for $\lambda = 1$, the alternative with the maximum aggregated achievement is obtained. Finally, we have included an intermediate solution, represented by the value of $\lambda = 0.5$.

2.2.5. Interactive steps

The model proposed has an additional strength that is the possibility of interacting with the decision makers in order to find out their preferences both for the diverse components of the model and for the results obtained. This idea of adding an interactive component in the GP models has been successfully used in other studies (Aldea et al., 2014), or this technique has even been hybridized with group decision models (Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2016). For our study, information has been requested from the decision maker on three elements of the model: the criteria finally selected (Interaction 1 in the flow chart), the weight given to each criterion (Interaction 2), and, finally, for the EGP model, the solution chosen from any of the three possible solutions presented to the DM (Interaction 3).

Interaction 1 permits the selection of the criteria included in this study, responding to the opinions of the DM but excluding, as mentioned before, carbon criterion. These opinions have been collected personally on visits to the case study chosen. As for Interaction 2, this consists of obtaining the weights given by the DM to each criterion, using for this purpose a procedure employing pairwise comparisons, based on Saaty’s verbal scale (Saaty, 1977). In addition, the DM was asked about acceptable values of the targets for each criterion, in terms of their distance from the ideal value, by means of a questionnaire sent by e-mail. Table 2 shows the weights and targets associated with the criteria obtained through both interactions. Finally, a third interaction was performed (by e-mail and telephone) to find out which of the solutions generated by the EGP model seemed to be the most attractive, according to the values of the coefficient λ .

Table 2
Weights and targets associated with each criterion.

	Weights	Target (% of the ideal value)
VOL	0.081	90
NPV	0.010	70
H	0.037	90
F	0.186	90
A	0.186	90
RA	0.062	90
NDRA	0.438	90

VOL: Harvest volume (10³m³), **NPV:** Net Present Value (10³€), **H:** Even flow harvest volume (10³m³), **F:** Forest ending inventory (10³m³), **A:** Area control (ha), **RA:** Total retained area (ha), **NDRA:** Non-declining retained area (ha).

Table 3
Results obtained in the EGP model for the three cases considered.

Variable	$\lambda = 0.5$	$\lambda = 0.5$	$\lambda = 1$
VOL	2,786	2,506	2,964
NPV	23,152	19,828	23,849
H	1,802	406	406
F	567	270	270
A	1,852	618	618
RA	1,892	1,555	1,048
NDRA	321	183	183
Carbon	4,160	4,280	4,075
agrR	1,256	954	408
disR	225	190	229

VOL: Harvest volume (10^3m^3), NPV: Net Present Value ($10^3€$), H: Even flow harvest volume deviation (10^3m^3), F: Forest ending inventory deviation (10^3m^3), A: Area control deviation (ha), RA: Total retained area (considering aggregated, dispersed and black vulture nest protection areas) (ha), NDRA: Non-declining retained area deviation (ha), Carbon: Carbon balance (10^3tC), agrR: Aggregated area (ha), disR: Dispersed area (ha).

3. Results

Table 3 shows the results of the EGP model according to the three values of λ considered. In addition to the results of the seven criteria contemplated for this case study, the values of the retained areas (aggregated and dispersed), and the carbon associated with each solution have been introduced as auxiliary rows. It should be pointed out that the sum of the retained areas, aggregated and dispersed, does not give the total retained area because the total includes the area initially retained in the forest for the protection of the black vulture species (411 ha). Also, in Table 3, the solution $\lambda = 0.5$ has been shaded grey, since this was the one chosen by the decision maker as being the best strategy to apply in the case study according to the third interaction previously mentioned.

Due to its importance for the future management of Valsain forest, the total retained area criterion was selected in order to analyse its evolution over the planning horizon in accordance with the solutions obtained above. Fig. 3 shows this evolution that includes the retained area, aggregated or dispersed, and the area initially retained because of the presence of black vulture nests in each period.

Additionally, for the solution chosen ($\lambda = 0.5$), the evolution of the new retained area, as dispersed (disR) and aggregated (agrR), is shown in each period. Both values, in addition to the area initially retained for the protection of black vulture nests, supply the value of the total area retained (RA) in each period, as shown in Fig. 4.

Next comes the interaction existing between the criteria of the area retained over the planning horizon with respect to the timber volume harvested in each period. Fig. 5 shows the evolution of the total retained area (RA) in relation to the harvested area (HA) in the ten periods into which the planning horizon is divided. The values presented correspond to the solution chosen ($\lambda = 0.5$).

Fig. 3. Total retained area (RA) per period in Valsain forest.

Fig. 4. Aggregated and dispersed retention per period for the chosen solution ($\lambda = 0.5$) in Valsain forest.

Fig. 5. Interaction of the retained area (RA) criteria and the harvested area (HA) per period in Valsain forest for the chosen solution ($\lambda = 0.5$).

4. Discussion

In this study, a methodology has been designed based on the multi-criteria decision making theory to integrate biodiversity conservation into a strategic forest planning model. In spite of multiple aspects to be considered, this ecosystem service has been quantified through a proxy such as an uncut area linked to a silvicultural system based on variable retention. Thus, it is possible to anticipate the initial spatial distribution of this area without cuttings over the planning horizon, and its possible conflict with other criteria considered in the forest management plan.

Analysing the results given in Table 3, for the most balanced solution ($\lambda = 0$), the maximum value of the retained area (1,892 ha) is obtained, although this area does not meet the condition of being non-decreasing in each period (NDRA). Besides, this solution does not reach any of the three criteria targets associated with the idea of a normal forest, although its deviations in relation to the ideal values are not very important. On the other hand, the last two models ($\lambda = 0.5$, $\lambda = 1$) reach the proposed target for all the technical criteria, and these solutions guarantee an almost even flow harvest volume per period, ensuring a minimum volume stock at the end of the planning horizon and fulfilling the age class regulation. As would be expected, the most significant differences between the three cases considered correspond to the aggregated retained area. Thus, these values decrease from the most balanced solution to the most efficient one. However, if we compare these solutions (Table 3) with those established in the pay-off matrix (Table 1), it can be seen that the multi-criteria models provide more balanced and attractive solutions for the decision maker.

One of the most immediate measures that could be adopted to improve objectives related to biodiversity conservation would be to reduce the area associated with final cuttings, thus increasing the retained area (Zobel et al., 2015). In relation to the results shown in Table 3, this situation that *a priori*, could imply a decrease both in the objectives and in the volume or the NPV, is not clearly perceived. This means that it is not by retaining a larger area ($\lambda = 0$) that a lower value of these criteria is obtained than the value for the intermediate solution ($\lambda = 0.5$); this implies that the trade-offs are not as linear as might be expected. For instance, it can be verified how the solution with the more extensive retained area involves fewer attractive solutions with regard to criteria

associated with the idea of a normal forest. However, in the literature, some examples are cited in which increasing the retained area does not cause a considerable reduction in the NPV (Bravo and Diaz-Balteiro, 2004). Nonetheless, unlike recent works (Augustynczyk et al., 2018), in this study, it was not proposed initially to calculate the cost of applying a silviculture based on variable retention systems. Finally, the same as in other studies (Eyvindson et al., 2018), it was proved that the solutions nearest to the fulfilment of the criterion of even flow harvest volume imply declines in other environmental criteria (e.g. retained area, carbon).

Furthermore, although the retention can vary in each case analysed, depending on the ecosystem services considered (Yoshida et al., 2017), this type of studies are of great interest when they are integrated into a strategic planning model. Therefore, it is helpful to introduce legal constraints that lead to the application of certain types of silviculture due to the presence of protected species or to the declaration of a new protection figure. Also, it allows us to find out the opportunity cost of not cutting a certain area of the forest, or, in short, to adopt a specific silvicultural alternative with biodiversity conservation objectives, an essential aspect in this decision making (Mori et al., 2017). Besides, these types of models permit the decision makers to understand the consequences of choosing one solution or another, or of giving a higher weight to a particular criterion (Lundström et al., 2018). In fact, it should be remembered that the solutions proposed are directly influenced by the manager's preferences. In this line, a subsequent exercise could be to incorporate the preferences not only of the manager but other stakeholders. In fact, we should not forget that the integration of the preferences of diverse stakeholders is an open question in the forestry sphere (Rönqvist et al., 2015), although models applied to forest management based on similar methodologies to those employed in this article have been proposed (Diaz-Balteiro et al., 2013).

Ideally, the model designed in this study should be complemented with a predictive model on the evolution of the black vulture populations. However, this is a complex issue both due to the number of variables involved and to the lack of some knowledge in this respect, such as what the maximum size of the population could be. However, one way to make this planning easier would be to use a tactical type model, which could even point out potential areas of nest exclusion in terms of variables associated with noise (Iglesias-Merchán et al., 2016). Another option could be, following Bagdon et al. (2016), to calculate an index for each stand according to its capacity to give shelter to at least one pair of black vultures over the planning horizon. Other future lines of work could be the inclusion of non-deterministic assumptions regarding the criteria considered in this model (Yousefpour et al., 2012; Pasalodos-Tato et al., 2013). In addition, in the future we aim to incorporate other nature contributions to people (NCP) into the analysis,

Appendix A1

Definition of model inputs

Constants

T is the length of the planning horizon.

t is the time period.

$L = T/t$ is the number of periods in which the planning horizon is divided.

ts is the time span that defines the final age class.

$S = T/ts$ is the number of final age classes, taking into account the range of years in which regeneration can occur.

B is the total forest area.

B_i is the area in stand i .

a is the percentage of maximum allowed total retained area.

b is the minimum harvest area when x_{ij} prescriptions are chosen.

$mAge$ and $MAge$ are the minimum and maximum harvest ages during the planning horizon, respectively.

V_{ijl} is the volume harvested per hectare in stand i , prescription j at period l .

F_z^i is the initial forest inventory on z site index.

using IPBES conceptual framework (Díaz et al., 2018). Notably, an objective addressing noise pollution (Iglesias-Merchán et al., 2014) could be included in a tactical forest management model derived from this strategic one. Finally, the integration will be done using a new multi-criteria model, an approach recommended by IPBES for incorporating values to support decision making (Pascual et al., 2017).

5. Conclusions

The model proposed has shown the feasibility of incorporating criteria associated with variable retention into strategic forest planning models. In synthesis, solutions can be obtained that give compatible and acceptable results both in criteria habitually considered in forest management (technical and production), and in other objectives oriented towards favouring biodiversity conservation. Specifically, it is a case of ensuring the viability of the populations of the black vulture species present in the case study. Also, this methodology allows the integration of decision makers' preferences into the different criteria defined, based on the importance and aspiration levels assigned for each criterion.

In their application to the case study presented, the aggregated retained area values are very different among the solutions considered. Although this does not imply notable changes in objectives like volume or the NPV, it does in the criteria related to the normal forest concept. However, the criterion of achieving an increasing retained area over the planning horizon is not strictly fulfilled in any of the three solutions, but in two of them, and it coincides with the target proposed. Lastly, this methodology allows us to quantify the opportunity cost derived from the introduction of biodiversity conservation measures in a strategic forest planning model.

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BVN is the Black Vulture Nest protection area.
 CF₀ is the initial investment and CF_t is the cash-flow per year.
 r is the discount rate.

Index sets

i is the number of stands.
 j is the number of prescriptions, defining a complete treatment schedule for each stand, following the Model I structure (Johnson and Scheurman, 1977).
 k is the number of initial age class
 l is the index of periods.
 z is the site index.

Variables

x_{ij} is the area harvested at prescription j in stand i.
 y_{ij} is the area retained at prescription j in stand i.
 ux_i is a binary variable to force decision variable x_i to take either a zero value or a value greater than, or equal to, the minimum harvest area designated by parameter b.
 disR_{ij} is the dispersed retention area when harvest prescriptions are chosen, which is expressed as a percentage of the corresponding area to the stand i.
 A_s is the area belonging to s final age class at the ending period.
 F_z^f is the ending forest inventory from site index z.
 SV_{ij} is the total standing volume at prescription j in stand i.

Criteria

VOL is the volume harvested at the end of the planning horizon.
 NPV is the Net Present Value at the end of the planning horizon.
 H_l is the even flow harvest volume per period l.
 F_z is the forest ending inventory for each site class z.
 A_s is the area control for each age class s.
 RA is the retention area at the end of the planning horizon.
 NDRA_l is the non-declining retained area per period l.

Definition of EGP model

[1] **Achievement function**

$$\text{MIN} = (1 - \lambda) \cdot D + \lambda \cdot \left(w_{VOL} \cdot \left(\frac{n_{VOL}}{R_{VOL}} \right) + w_{NPV} \cdot \left(\frac{n_{NPV}}{R_{NPV}} \right) + w_H \cdot \left(\frac{(n_H + p_H)}{R_H} \right) + w_F \cdot \left(\frac{(n_z F + p_z F)}{R_F} \right) + w_A \cdot \left(\frac{(n_s A + p_s A)}{R_A} \right) + w_{RA} \cdot \left(\frac{n_{RA}}{R_{RA}} \right) + w_{NDRA} \cdot \left(\frac{(n_{lNDRA} + p_{lNDRA})}{R_{NDRA}} \right) \right)$$

[2] **Timber harvest volume (VOL)**

$$[2.1] \text{VOL} = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{l=1}^L V_{ijl} \cdot (x_{ij} (1 - \text{dis}R_{ij})) \quad \forall i, j, l$$

$$[2.2] \text{VOL} + n_{VOL} - p_{VOL} = \text{VOL}^*$$

[3] **Net present value (NPV)**

$$[3.1] \text{NPV} = -CF_0 + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

$$[3.2] \text{NPV} + n_{NPV} - p_{NPV} = \text{NPV}^*$$

[4] **Even flow harvest volume (H)**

$$[4.1] H_l = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J V_{ijl} \cdot x_{ij} \cdot (1 - \text{dis}R_i) \quad \forall l$$

$$[4.2] H_{l+1} - H_l + n_l H - p_l H = 0, \quad l = 1, \dots, L - 1$$

[5] **Forest ending inventory (F)**

$$[5.1] F_z^f = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J SV_{ij} \cdot x_{ij} \quad \forall z$$

$$[5.2] F_z^f + n_z F - p_z F \geq F_z^i$$

[6] **Area Control (A)**

$$[6.1] A_s = \sum_{l=1}^2 x_{ijl} + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J x_{ij}, \quad s = 1$$

$$[6.2] A_s = \sum_{l=2k-1}^{2k} x_{kjl}, \quad 1 < s \leq S$$

$$[6.3] A_s + n_s A - p_s A = B/S$$

[7] Retention area (RA)

$$[7.1] RA = BVN + agrR + disR$$

$$[7.2] agrR = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J y_{ij}$$

$$[7.3] RA = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J BVN + (y_{ij} + disR_{ij} \cdot x_{ij}) \quad \forall i, j$$

$$[7.4] RA + n_{RA} - p_{RA} \geq RA^*$$

[8] Non-declining retained area (NDRA)

$$[8.1] RA_{l+1} + n_l NDRA - p_l NDRA > RA_l, \quad l = 1, \dots, L - 1$$

$$[8.2] RA_{l+1} + n_l NDRA - p_l NDRA > RA_l, \quad l = 1, \dots, L - 1$$

Subject to**[9] Area accounting**

$$[9.1] \sum_{j=1}^J x_{ij} + y_{ij} = B_i \quad \forall i, j$$

$$[9.2] \sum_{i=1}^I B_i = B$$

[10] Maximum allowed Retention Area

$$\sum_{i=1}^I RA_{ij} \leq a \cdot B, \quad \forall j$$

[11] Auxiliary variables domain

$$ux_i \in \{0, 1\}$$

[12] Minimum harvest area

$$[12.1] x_{ij} - b \cdot ux_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i, j$$

$$[12.2] x_{ij} = 0 \quad \forall i, j; \quad x_{ij} < b$$

[13] Minimum and maximum harvest age

$$x_{ij} = 0 \quad \forall i, j, \quad k < mAge \wedge k > MAge; \quad \forall l$$

[14] Non-negativity constraints

$$[14.1] x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, j$$

$$[14.2] y_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, j$$

$$[14.3] n_{VOL}, n_{NPV}, n_l H, n_k F, n_s A, n_{RA}, n_l NDRA \geq 0$$

$$[14.4] p_{VOL}, p_{NPV}, p_l H, p_k F, p_s A, p_{RA}, p_l NDRA \geq 0$$

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